

Stability Constants of Copper(II), Nickel(II), Cobalt(II) and Zinc(II) Complexes with Some Hydroxycoumarins

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The new bidentate Schiff bases of 8-formyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (FHMB) with aniline (FHMBANIL) or *p*-methylaniline (FHMBMANIL) have been synthesised and characterised by analytical and spectral data. Proton-ligand formation constants of these compounds and metal-ligand formation constants of their metal chelates with Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Zn^{II} have been determined *pH*-metrically in 70% (v/v) aqueous methanol at 35°. Plots of $\bar{n}/(1-\bar{n})[L]$ vs $(2-\bar{n})[L]/(1-\bar{n})$ were found to be good straight lines with definite slopes indicating the formation of both 1:1 and 1:2 complexes. The order of stability constants with respect to metal ions is in conformity with the Irving-Williams natural order of stabilities and with respect to ligands, FHMB < FHMBANIL < FHMBMANIL.

MUCH interest is paid by recent investigators to the study of metal complexes of coumarins and Schiff bases since they are becoming increasingly important as biochemical, analytical and antimicrobial reagents. This prompted us to study the synergistic behaviour of these two moieties on the complexing tendencies with metal ions. In the present investigation the Schiff bases of 8-formyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (FHMB) with aniline (FHMBANIL) and *p*-methyl aniline (FHMBMANIL) have been synthesised and their interaction with Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Zn^{II} has been studied *pH*-metrically.

Experimental

The Schiff bases (FHMBANIL and FHMBMANIL) were prepared by refluxing (1 h) equimolar quantities of FHMB and aniline (freshly distilled) or *p*-methyl aniline in methanol. Yellow crystals which separated on cooling in ice were filtered, washed with 50% methanol and repeatedly crystallised from methanol to get a tlc pure sample.

FHMBANIL, m.p. 160° (Found: C, 72.88; H, 4.59; N, 5.08. C₁₇H₁₅NO₃ calcd C, 73.11; H, 4.65; N, 5.01%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3000-3200 br (OH), 1725 (C=O lactonic) and 1615 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ (60 MHz; CDCl₃; TMS internal ref.) 2.46 (3H, t, 4-CH₃), 6.0 (1H, s, 3-H), 6.8-7.8 (7H, m, Ar-H), 9.32 (1H, s, CH=N) and 15.0 (1H, s, OH, D₂O exchangeable).

FHMBMANIL, m.p. 190° (Found: C, 73.29; H, 5.18; N, 4.71. C₁₈H₁₇NO₃ calcd. C, 73.72; H, 5.11; N, 4.77%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3000-3225 br (OH), 1725 (C=O lactonic) and 1610 (C=N); δ 2.40 (6H, t, CH₃), 6.0 (1H, s, 3-H), 6.8-7.6 (6H, m, Ar-H), 9.03 (1H, s, CH=N) and 15.20 (1H, s, OH, D₂O exchangeable).

Based on the above analytical and spectral data structure (1) was assigned to these Schiff bases.

FHMB, X=O; FHMBANIL, X=C₆H₅N-;
FHMBMANIL, X=*p*-Me-C₆H₄N-.

Proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants were determined using the Irving-Rossotti *pH*-titration technique¹ in 70% v/v methanol water (I=0.1 M NaClO₄) at 35°. The experimental details are those described earlier². As the earlier studies were made in 50% (v/v) aqueous methanol medium, the stability constants of metal(II)-FHMB were redetermined under the present experimental conditions for a better comparison.

Results and Discussion

The titration curves and the formation curves of metal(II)-FHMBMANIL system are given in Fig. 1.

In the acid region, the ligand titration curve (Fig. 1) lies above the acid curve due to the basic property of nitrogens to accept protons from strongly acid medium. However, in the basic region, it lies below the acid curve due to the release of -OH protons. From the *pH* and \bar{n}_H data the values of log K_{OH} and log K_{NH} were evaluated

coincide well with those theoretical \bar{n} values calculated on the assumption of the formation of both 1:1 and 1:2 but not when only a 1:1 complex was assumed. The standard deviations for all the metal-ligand systems are found to be less than ± 0.01 . The small differences between K_1 and K_2 suggest the simultaneous formation of both 1:1 and 1:2 chelates in solution.

The distribution diagrams drawn for the various species indicate the formation of both ML and ML_2 complexes in significant proportions. As a typical case the distribution curves for the Ni^{II} system are given in Fig. 2. Similar results were obtained for other systems. Thus, the quantities of M(II) and ML_2 changed monotonically as a function of free ligand concentration, whereas the amount of the intermediate species, ML, attained a certain maximum value.

Fig. 2. Distribution diagram for Ni^{II} -FHMBANIL system.

The order of stability constants of all these metal-ligand systems are in conformity with Irving-Williams natural order of stabilities. With respect to the ligands, the stability sequence, FHMB < FHMBANIL < FHMBMANIL, is in accordance with their relative basicities. Such a direct correlation of stabilities with ligand basicities is based on the assumption that base strength is a measure of the σ -bonding ability of the ligands with metal ions. Since, the basicities of these ligands are not of the same order, these correlations would not, further, throw any light on the steric and π -interactions in the metal-

ligand system⁵. This can be achieved by a comparison of the 'stability per unit base strength', defined as the ratio of stability constants to the total basic strength of the ligand, i.e. $\log (\beta_n/\beta_n^H)$ for various metal complexes⁵⁻⁷. These ratios (Table 3) for Cu^{II} complexes are significantly greater

TABLE 3—STABILITY CONSTANT PER UNIT BASE STRENGTH FOR VARIOUS METAL-LIGAND SYSTEMS

Metal	FHMB	FHMBANIL	FHMBMANIL
Cu^{II}	1.56	1.28	1.27
Ni^{II}	1.18	0.79	0.80
Co^{II}	1.08	0.71	0.75
Zn^{II}	1.00	0.67	0.71

when compared to Zn^{II} while for Ni^{II} and Co^{II} they are in between the two, indicating the extensive π -interactions in copper chelates. The decreased values of these ratios from FHMB to FHMBANIL and FHMBMANIL may be attributed to the steric hindrance caused by the phenyl group present in the latter compounds.

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